

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF HPTLC METHOD
FOR ESTIMATION OF ALCAFTADINE IN BULK AND ITS
FORMULATION****Bhushan J. Mali*, Rajendra D. Wagh**Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, DCS's, A.R.A. College of Pharmacy, Nagaon, Dist:
Dhule (MS) India 424 005**Abstract:**

A simple, precise, accurate and rapid high performance thin layer chromatographic method has been developed and validated for estimation of Alcaftadine in bulk and Eye Drops. The chromatographic development was carried out on aluminium plates precoated with silica gel 60 F₂₅₄, as a stationary phase. A mixture of Chloroform: Methanol: Triethylamine (4:1:0.5 v/v/v) was used as mobile phase which offered a compact and dense spot of Alcaftadine. Detection was carried out densitometrically at 282 nm. The R_f value of drug was found to be 0.45 ± 0.02. The method was validated with respect to linearity, accuracy, precision, robustness and ruggedness. The calibration curve was found to be linear over a range of 250-1500 ng/μl. Recovery studies were performed at three concentration levels to defend suitability, accuracy and precision of developed method. The LOD and LOQ for Alcaftadine were 9.27ng and 28.1ng respectively. The proposed HPTLC method was found to provide a faster and cost-effective quantitative control for routine analysis of Alcaftadine as bulk drug and in its pharmaceutical formulation.

Key words: Alcaftadine, HPTLC, Validation, Eye drops, LOD, LOQ.

Corresponding author:**Bhushan J. Mali,**DCS's, A.R.A. College of Pharmacy, Mumbai Agra Highway, Nagaon,
Dist: Dhule (MS) India 424 005

Contact: (02562)261021

Mobile: +919421535118

Email: bjm3006@gmail.com

QR code

Please cite this article in press Bhushan J. Mali*, Rajendra D. Wagh, *Development and Validation Of HPTLC Method For Estimation Of Alcaftadine In Bulk And Its Formulation*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2021; 08(1).

INTRODUCTION:

Analysis of pharmaceutical compounds and newer drugs is commonly used in all the stages of drug discovery and development process. These analytical techniques provide more accurate and precised data, not only supporting drug discovery and development but also postmarket surveillance [1].

Thin layer chromatography studies are among the key identity tests in most pharmacopoeial monographs. An extension of TLC is high-performance thin layer chromatography (HPTLC) is robust, simplest, rapid, and efficient tool in quantitative analysis of compounds. HPTLC is an analytical technique based on TLC, but with enhancements intended to increase the resolution of the compounds to be separated and to allow quantitative analysis of the compounds [2].

Alcaftadine (ALC) is H1 histamine receptor antagonist indicated for the prevention of itching associated with allergic conjunctivitis [3, 4]. It is a broad-spectrum antihistamine known to display high affinity toward histamine H1 and H2 receptors and a lower affinity for H4 receptors [5]. It also exhibits modulatory action on immune cell recruitment and mast cell stabilizing effects. It is chemically known as 6, 11-dihydro-11-(1-methyl-4-piperidinylidene)-5H-imidazo [2, 1-b] benzazepine-3-carboxaldehyde [6]. The chemical structure is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Structure of Alcaftadine

A literature survey on Alcaftadine revealed that several analytical methods were reported for the

analysis of ALC including high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) [7], spectrophotometry [8], UPLC/MS method [9] and stability indicating TLC-Densitometric method [10]. So far, to the best of our knowledge no simple HPTLC method has been reported for estimation of ALC.

This encourages us to undertake this work, so that quantitative estimation of ALC can be done and hence can be used for routine analysis of bulk and formulation as well. The present study describes the development and validation of a simple, precise, sensitive and accurate HPTLC method for the determination of ALC in bulk and formulation. The proposed method is optimized and validated as per the International Conference on Harmonization (ICH) guidelines. [11, 12]

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Chemicals and reagents:

Pure standard ALC was kindly gifted from Sun Pharmaceutical Industries Ltd, Goregaon (E), Mumbai (Maharashtra), India. Cafta™ Eye Drops were purchased from local pharmacy each one ml is labeled to contain 2.5 mg ALC. All the other reagents and solvents used were of analytical grade.

Selection of chromatographic layer

Identification and determination of the drug was performed on (10 cm × 10 cm. layer thickness 0.2 mm, E. Merck, Darmstadt, Germany) aluminium backed silica gel 60 F₂₅₄ TLC plates, pre-washed with methanol.

Selection and optimization of mobile phase

Initially, different ratio of methanol, chloroform, n-propanol and toluene were tried but tailing of spots were observed. Finally, the mobile phase Chloroform: methanol: triethylamine (4: 1: 0.5 % v/v) gives good resolution, sharp and symmetrical peak. The optimization trials for mobile phase are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Optimization of mobile phase

Sr. no.	Solvents	Proportion (mL)	R _f of ALC
1	Methanol	5.0	Tailing
2	n- propanol	5.0	0.85
3	Toluene	5.0	0.20
4	Toluene : n-propanol	3.0 : 2.0	0.75
5	Toluene : Methanol	3.5 : 1.5	0.80
6	Chloroform : methanol	4.0 : 1.0	0.43 with tailing
7	Chloroform : Methanol : Triethylamine	4 : 1 : 0.5	0.45

Instrumentation and chromatographic conditions:

The samples were spotted in the form of bands of width of 6 mm with a Camag 100 μ L sample syringe (Hamilton, Bonaduz, Switzerland) on precoated silica gel aluminium plate 60 F₂₅₄ (20cm \times 10cm with 0.2 mm thickness), supplied by Anchrom technologists, (Mumbai) using a CAMAG Linomat 5 sample applicator (Switzerland). A constant application rate of 200 nl/sec was employed and space between two bands was 15.4 mm. The slit dimension was kept 6 mm \times 0.45 mm. The mobile phase consisted of Chloroform: Methanol: Triethylamine (4:1:0.5 v/v/v) was selected which gave sharp and symmetrical peak with Rf 0.45 as shown in Figure 2. The optimized chamber saturation time for mobile phase was 20 min at room temp (25°C \pm 2°C) and relative humidity 60% \pm 5%. The length of chromatogram run was approximately 8 cm. Subsequent to the development; TLC plates were dried in current of air with the help of an air dryer. Densitometric scanning was performed using Camag TLC scanner 3 in the absorbance mode at 282 nm and software used was winCATS 4.0.5. The source of radiation utilized was deuterium lamp emitting a continuous UV spectrum in the range of 400 - 200 nm.

Figure 2. Chromatogram of Standard ALC (Rf: 0.45)

Preparation of standard stock solution:

An accurately weighed quantity of 10 mg ALC was transferred to 10 ml volumetric flasks, dissolved in methanol and volume was made up to mark with the same solvent to obtain a working standard having concentration 1000 ng/ μ L.

Validation of method:

The method was validated as per the ICH guidelines in terms of its linearity, accuracy, intra-day and inter-day precision, robustness, ruggedness, LOD & LOQ.

Linearity (Calibration curve):

For linearity study, aliquots of 0.25, 0.5, 0.75, 1, 1.25 and 1.5 μ L of ALC from standard stock solution was applied on TLC plate with the help of microlitre syringe, using Linomat 5 sample applicator to obtain the concentration of 250, 500, 750, 1000, 1250 and 1500 ng / band. TLC plates were developed under above established conditions. Three dimensional overlay of HPTLC densitograms of standard plot of ALC are shown in Figure 3. Area under peak was recorded and plotted against concentration. The calibration curve is as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 3. Three Dimensional Overlay of HPTLC densitograms of Standard ALC

Figure 4. Calibration Curve for ALC

Accuracy/ Recovery:

The pre-analyzed samples were over spotted with extra 80, 100 and 120 % of the ALC from Eye drops on TLC plate. The total concentrations of the drug were determined (n=3), to check for the recovery of the drug at different levels in formulation.

Precision:

Repeatability of measurement of peak area was determined by spotting 1000 ng/spot of ALC. Precision of the method was assessed by intra-day and inter-day variations by spotting 500, 750, 1000 ng/spot of ALC on TLC plate on three different times within the same day (Intra-day) and on three different days (Inter-day).

Robustness:

Robustness of the method was performed by spotting 750 ng of drug on TLC plate by making small deliberate changes in chromatographic conditions like mobile phase composition and the effects on the results were examined. Mobile phases having different composition of chloroform: methanol: TEA (3.8:1.2:0.5 and 4.3:0.7:0.2 v/v) were tried and chromatograms were run. The amount of mobile phase was varied in the range of $\pm 5\%$. The chamber saturation time was varied by ± 5 min. Development distance was varied by ± 2 cm. Chromatograms were run on these varied conditions to validate the robustness of the method.

Ruggedness:

Ruggedness of the method was performed by spotting 750 ng of ALC by two different analyst keeping same experimental and environmental conditions.

Limit of detection (LOD) and limit of quantification (LOQ):

In order to determine detection and quantification limit, concentrations in the lower part of the linear range of the calibration curve were used. ALC solutions of 250, 300, 350, 400, 450 and 500 ng/μl were prepared and applied in triplicate. The LOQ and LOD were calculated using equation $LOD = 3.3 \times N/B$ and $LOQ = 10 \times N/B$, where, N is standard deviation of the peak areas of the drugs (n=3), taken as a measure of noise and B is the slope of the corresponding calibration curve.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:**HPTLC method development:**

The TLC procedure was optimized with a view to develop method for determination of ALC. Optimization of mobile phase with chloroform:

methanol: triethylamine [4: 1: 0.5 (v/v)] gives sharp and symmetrical peak having R_f value of 0.45 ± 0.2 . It was observed that prewashing of TLC plates with methanol (followed by drying and activation) and pre-saturation of TLC chamber with mobile phase for 20 min ensures good reproducibility and peak shape of drugs.

Method Validation:**Linearity:**

The linear regression data for the calibration curves showed good linear relationship over the concentration range 250-1500 ng/μl. Linear regression equation was found to be $y = 13.936x - 1189.1$ ($r^2 = 0.9996$).

Accuracy/ Recovery:

The proposed method when used for extraction and subsequent estimation of drug from Eye drop dosage form after over spotting with 80, 100 and 120 % of additional drug; afforded recovery of 99.60 – 99.98 % as listed in Table 2.

Table 2: Results of recovery studies

Label claim (mg/ml)	Amount of standard drug added (%)	% Drug recovery*	% R.S.D.
2.5	80	99.60	0.67
	100	98.98	0.54
	120	99.63	0.61

*mean of three estimations at each level

Precision:

The precision of the developed HPTLC method was expressed in terms of % relative standard deviation (% RSD). The results depicted revealed high precision of the method is presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Intra-day and Inter-day Precision

Conc. (ng/μl)	Intra-day		Inter-day	
	% Amount found*	% R.S.D.	% Amount found*	% R.S. D
500	99.5	0.71	99.62	0.72
750	99.7	0.51	100.14	0.77
1000	99.61	0.24	100.04	0.96

*mean of three estimations at each level

Robustness:

The standard deviation of peak areas was calculated for each parameter and % R.S.D. was found to be less than 2 %. The results are shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Robustness of the method

Parameters	S.D. of peak area	% R.S.D.*
Mobile phase composition	42.48	1.24
Mobile phase volume	38.67	1.12
Development distance	34.75	0.96
Duration of saturation	28.48	1.38

*mean of three estimations at each level

Ruggedness:

Ruggedness of the method was performed by applying 750 ng by two different analyst keeping same experimental and environmental conditions. The results summarized in Table 5.

Table 5: Results of Ruggedness study

Analyst	%Amount found of SAF (Mean \pm S.D.)	%R.S.D.*
I	99.24 \pm 0.58	0.59
II	99.37 \pm 0.92	0.93

*mean of three estimations at each level

LOD and LOQ:

Detection limit and quantification limit for ALC was found to be 9.27ng and 28.1ng respectively. This indicates adequate sensitivity of the method.

CONCLUSION:

The HPTLC method for the estimation of Alcaftadine was developed and validated as per ICH guidelines and the method was found to simple, precise, accurate and reproducible and can be used for determination of ALC in Eye drops. Moreover, proposed method also indicates no interference of excipients when applied to Pharmaceutical formulation. Future plan includes development of same drug either in alone or in combination by more sophisticated techniques.

Abbreviations:

Thin layer chromatography (TLC), High Performance Thin Layer Chromatography (HPTLC), Limit of Detection (LOD), Limit of Quantification (LOQ), Alcaftadine (ALC).

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS:

Authors are thankful to Sun Pharmaceutical Industries Ltd, Goregaon (E), Mumbai (Maharashtra), India for providing gift sample of Alcaftadine.

REFERENCES:

1. Sweedler JV. The continued evolution of hyphenated instruments. *Anal Bioanal Chem.* 2002;373:321–2
2. Reich E, Schibli A. Stationary Phases for Planar Separations - Plates for Modern TLC. *LC GC.* 2005; 23:58–69.
3. Bohets H, McGowan C, Mannens G, Schroeder N, Edwards-Swanson K, and Shapiro A. Clinical pharmacology of alcaftadine, a novel antihistamine for the prevention of allergic conjunctivitis. *Journal of ocular pharmacology and therapeutics.* 2011; 27(2):87-195.
4. Greiner JV, Edwards-Swanson K, and Ingerman A. Evaluation of alcaftadine 0.25% ophthalmic solution in acute allergic conjunctivitis at 15 minutes and 16 hours after instillation versus placebo and olopatadine 0.1%. *Clinical ophthalmology (Auckland, NZ).* 2011; 5:87.
5. Namdar R, and Valdez C. Alcaftadine: a topical antihistamine for use in allergic conjunctivitis. *Drugs of today (Barcelona, Spain: 1998).* 2011; 47(12): 883-890.
6. Chemistry Review
http://www.accessdata.fda.gov/drugsatfda_docs/nda/2010/022134s000 ChemR.pdf. Accessed 16 Mar 2015).
7. Mishra PR, Satone D, and Meshram DB. Development and Validation of HPLC Method for the Determination of Alcaftadine in Bulk Drug and its Ophthalmic Solution. *J Chromatogr Sep Tech.* 2016; 7(312): 2.
8. Mishra PR, Inamdar P, Jamdar P, Patel N, Rohit M, Satone D, and Meshram DB. Development and validation of UV-spectrophotometry and the first order derivative using the area under curve method for the estimation of alcaftadine in bulk and its ophthalmic dosage form. *FS J Pharm Res.* 2015; 4(1): 9-13.
9. Chavan BB, Kalariya PD, Srinivas R. and Talluri MK. Alcaftadine: Selective Separation and Characterization of Degradation Products by LC–

- QTOF-MS/MS. *Chromatographia*. 2018; 81(4): 631-638.
10. Aya T. Soudi, Ola G. Hussein, Eman S. Elzanfaly, Hala E. Zaazaa, Mohamed Abdelkawy. Stability Indicating TLC–Densitometric Method for Determination of Alcaftadine in Presence of its Degradation Products and Dosage form Preservatives. *Research J. Pharm. and Tech.* 2020; 13(11):5171-5176.
 11. ICH–Guidelines Q2A (1995) Validation of Analytical Procedures: Definition and terminology (CPMP III/5626/94) Geneva, Switzerland March.
 12. ICH–Guidelines Q2B (1996) Validation of Analytical Procedures: Methodology (CPMP/ICH/281/95) Geneva, Switzerland November.